

THE CONCEPTS OF “EDUCATIONAL SERVICES” AND THEIR ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

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The modern world cannot be imagined without educated people. Everyone has at least a basic education. In this connection, the education system must be considered as one of the most important parts of the life of a modern society, which is necessary for the successful functioning of any state. High-quality education of citizens can increase the level of rapid development of all sectors of the country's economy, which determines the future of the country, its security and economic development, which in turn increases competitiveness in relation to other countries, and ensures its independence.¹ In addition, the development of telecommunications technology, globalization, the expansion of international trade and other similar processes generate demand for education.

The importance of this sector of the economy is also reflected in the Education Law, which was adopted by the Legislative Chamber on May 19, 2020 and approved by the Senate on August 7, 2020, in order to regulate relations in the field of education. For example, Chapter 3 of the aforementioned law defines the term education: “education is a systemic process aimed at providing students with deep theoretical knowledge, skills and practical skills, as well as at the formation of general educational and professional knowledge, skills and abilities, and the development of abilities”.² In the process of education, certain educational levels are achieved. Educational activity is divided by the legislator into two types:

- the first type is an activity that is carried out in accordance with educational standards (on the basis of general educational programs);
- the second type - additional educational services, in which the volume and content are regulated by state standards, but at the same time, additions from the service provider are welcome.

In addition, the Law states that private and public educational institutions have the right to provide paid additional educational services to those who wish, such as training in additional educational programs, teaching special courses and cycles of disciplines, classes with students in-depth study of subjects and other services in the field of education.

Recently, the state has adopted a lot of legal documents in the field of development and improvement of the quality of education of the population. For example, “in order to form the knowledge and skills of school students, educate them in the spirit of devotion to national and universal values, increase the authority of the teaching profession and the quality of teachers,

¹ Мухаммедов М.М. и др. «Хизмат курсатиш сохаси ва туризмни ривожлантиришнинг назарий асослари». - Самарканд.: «Zarafshop», 2017, С.117.

² Закон Республики Узбекистан «Об образовании» принятый ЗП 19.05.2020 г., одобренный Сенатом 07.08.2020г.

improve textbooks and educational and methodological complexes based on modern requirements, build modern models of public education institutions meeting international standards" Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" dated 01.28.2022 was adopted. No. UP-60 and "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022 - 2026" dated 11.05.2022. for No. UP-134.

Today, educational activities are identified with educational services, in which many definitions are given that are different in content and similar in meaning. For example, A.Skalkin in his article gives the following definition: "Educational services are an element of educational activity that has special goals and subjective composition. The goals of educational services are the transfer of knowledge, skills, the formation of professional skills and their development by students. The subjects of educational services are educational organizations represented by the teaching staff and students who wish to receive education of one level or another."³

Another definition, no less important in meaning, is given in his work by V.N.Zotov: "an educational service is the amount of educational and scientific information transmitted to a citizen in the form of a sum of knowledge of a public and special nature, as well as practical skills transmitted to a citizen according to a specific program".⁴

Agreeing with all the above definitions, we can conclude that an educational service is a relationship between those who want to receive certain knowledge and those who provide this knowledge on a reimbursable or non-reimbursable basis. Educational services are directly involved in the formation of human capital, since the process of providing services takes place in conjunction with the creation of spiritual values, the transformation and development of the student's personality, and this, in turn, helps to reduce the country's poverty level.

Educational services have their own specifics, which are manifested both in traditional characteristics and in features that are unique to educational services. One of the specifics of educational services is that they belong to the category of "public goods". Another is the impossibility of their direct monetary measurement. The price mechanism is often unable to reflect all the costs of producing educational services. This is explained by the absence of a material form and material expression of the results, their use in the course of this activity, and also by the fact that they contain a useful effect in themselves. If in the material sphere it is relatively easy to measure them quantitatively, for example, in pieces or kilograms per unit of output, then in relation to educational services this is difficult to implement, i.e. services generate intangible goods. These benefits are not covered by the right of ownership: the result of the provision of educational services is the receipt of a certain level of education, while the paid nature of the services is implied. Services are provided for a fee. At the same time, the educational process in state educational institutions within the framework of the main educational programs and state educational standards is free of charge, and an agreement on

³ Скалина А.Н. Понятие образовательных услуг и правовые основы их оказания // Материалы VIII Международной студенческой научной конференции «Студенческий научный форум» URL: <a href=<https://scienceforum.ru/2016/article/2016024643> https://scienceforum.ru/2016/article/2016024643 (дата обращения: 30.03.2023).</p>

⁴ Зотов, В.Н. Разработка стратегии и тактики маркетинговой деятельности вузов на рынке образовательных услуг и научно-технической продукции: Автореф. на соискание ученой степени кандидата экономических наук. – М.: РЭА им. Г.В. Плеханова, 1997. – 21 с.

the provision of educational services is not drawn up for the implementation of these processes.

In addition, there is another distinguishing feature of educational services - the ambiguity of the goals set for organizations providing these services. As a rule, the activities of an educational institution are not directly aimed at achieving profit, i.e. many of their interests are connected with the growth of well-being, which involves "receiving the profit necessary to ensure expanded reproduction".

Based on some theoretical aspects of economic theory, educational services can be classified as pure private goods. A significant positive external effect of educational services also allows them to be classified as socially significant private goods.

Being one of the types of socio-economic benefits, educational services are of an additional nature in a non-core educational institution, exceed the state educational standard, and the costs necessary for the production and consumption of such activities require adequate compensation. But at the same time, it is possible to increase the volume of educational services offered by selecting qualified teachers, expanding the classroom fund, additional funding, etc.

Knowledge, skills, and specialties obtained in the course of providing educational services, on the one hand, are a motive for the consumer when he enters the market of educational services. An individual seeks with the help of educational services to be able to choose the most suitable niche for him in the labor market. At the same time, in the conditions of competition between educational institutions, he has the opportunity to choose, focusing on various factors. In terms of content, educational services are characterized by the knowledge, skills and abilities that the consumer of educational services acquires, as well as the specialty that he receives in the end result.

Among the factors influencing the consumer's motivation when choosing educational services are both the main and additional advantages of an educational organization. An important role for the consumer is played by the timing, type and form of training, the level of qualification of teachers of an educational institution, the material base of an educational organization, which includes classrooms for classes, their equipment with modern teaching aids, etc. In turn, to attract potential consumers of educational services, such advantages as various additional courses for advanced training or retraining, diplomas, certificates, free counseling, and certain benefits are applied. Thus, from the point of view of economics, concepts such as "advanced product" and "potential product" are used to attract consumers. The desire of the consumer to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities that will help him gain advantages in the labor market determines another characteristic feature of educational services. This is the mutual activity of the provider of such a service, as well as its recipient. This feature distinguishes educational services from others, in most of which the client remains a passive party.

At the same time, such paid educational activities were not considered as entrepreneurial. Researchers of educational legislation identify both positive and negative aspects of introducing the concept of "educational services" into legal acts. As positive aspects, it is customary to single out the following aspects:

1. the introduction of this concept legalized paid forms of education;
2. the use of the concept of "educational services" in educational legislation allows the use of civil law forms of regulation of public relations in the field of education;

3. the introduction of this concept contributed to the development of competition in the market of educational services;

4. paid educational services made it possible to find additional non-state sources of funding for state educational institutions;

5. granting financial independence to some higher educational institutions and a number of powers of the Cabinet of Ministers and ministries, in particular, transferring the studies of foreign citizens from foreign universities to state universities in Uzbekistan and determining the internal regulations of students.⁵

All the above actions are aimed at creating conditions for the development of entrepreneurship and business, accelerating the process of implementing innovative developments in the field of science and education. For example, the Decree of the President “On the Concept for the Development of Higher Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” dated October 8, 2019 No. UP-5847 indicates plans to improve the education sector and educational services in Uzbekistan. This concept contributes to the internationalization of higher education in Uzbekistan and requires some universities to have an international rating. It should be noted that our country prioritizes improving the quality of all three levels of education (primary, secondary and higher), rather than focusing on one level of education. Approximately 44.4% of total social spending is allocated to finance large-scale education policy.

In addition, in recent years, in order to improve the quality of educational services, foreign scientists and specialists from leading universities and institutes of the world have been involved in the education system on the basis of distance learning and exchange of experience.

⁵ Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан «О мерах по предоставлению финансовой самостоятельности государственным высшим образовательным учреждениям» от 24.12.2021 г. № ПП-60

References:

1. Закон Республики Узбекистан «Об образовании» принятый ЗП 19.05.2020 г., одобренный Сенатом 07.08.2020 г.
2. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан «Об утверждении национальной программы по развитию народного образования в 2022 – 2026 годах» от 11.05.2022г. за № УП-134.
3. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан «О стратегии развития Нового Узбекистана на 2022 – 2026 годы» от 28.01.2022г. за № УП-60.
4. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан «Об утверждении концепции развития системы высшего образования Республики Узбекистан до 2030 года» от 08.10.2019 г. № УП-5847
5. Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан «О мерах по предоставлению финансовой самостоятельности государственным высшим образовательным учреждениям» от 24.12.2021 г. № ПП-60.
6. Зотов, В.Н. «Разработка стратегии и тактики маркетинговой деятельности вузов на рынке образовательных услуг и научно-технической продукции» Автореф. на соискание ученой степени кандидата экономических наук. – М.: РЭА им. Г.В. Плеханова, 1997. С. 21.
7. Мухаммедов М.М. и др. «Хизмат курсатиш сохаси ва туризмни ривожлантиришнинг назарий асослари». -Самарканд.: «Zarafshon», 2017, С.117.
8. Скалина А.Н. «Понятие образовательных услуг и правовые основы их оказания». Материалы VIII Международной студенческой научной конференции «Студенческий научный форум» 2016.

